

**Chemical composition and biological activities of the essential oil of *Melaleuca cajuputi*
from Dak Lak Province, Vietnam**

**Composição química e atividades biológicas do óleo essencial de *Melaleuca cajuputi* da
província de Dak Lak, Vietnã**

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MATERIALS AND METHODS

Chemicals

A homologous series of C₇–C₃₀ *n*-alkanes employed for retention index determination, Tween 80, α -glucosidase enzyme, and *p*-nitrophenyl- α -D-glucopyranoside (*p*NPG) were supplied by Sigma-Aldrich (St. Louis, MO, USA). All solvents and reagents used in the experiments were of analytical grade, including methanol, diethyl ether, and anhydrous sodium sulfate (Na₂SO₄). Microbiological media and standard antibiotic discs (gentamicin) were obtained from Merck (Darmstadt, Germany) and Oxoid Ltd. (Basingstoke, Hampshire, UK).

Essential oil isolation

Following collection, the leaves of *M. cajuputi* were carefully cleaned to remove extraneous materials, rinsed with distilled water, and left to drain at ambient temperature for approximately 2.5 h, then air-dried for an additional 2 h. A representative sample (100 g) of the finely chopped plant material was placed in a Clevenger-type apparatus and subjected to hydrodistillation with 1000 mL of distilled water for 3 h under controlled electric heating. The resulting distillate was condensed and allowed to separate into aqueous and essential oil layers. The essential oil phase was isolated using diethyl ether, dehydrated over Na₂SO₄, and concentrated under reduced pressure to afford the final essential oil.

GC-MS analysis of essential oil

The chemical composition of *M. cajuputi* essential oil was determined using a Trace GC Ultra-ITQ900 GC-MS system (Thermo Fisher Scientific, MA, USA), with data acquisition and processing carried out using MassFinder 4.0 software. Separation of volatile constituents was achieved on a fused-silica TG-SQC capillary column (30 m × 0.25 mm i.d., 0.25 μ m film thickness). The GC conditions were set as follows: injector temperature, 250 °C; detector

temperature, 260 °C; oven temperature programmed from 60 to 260 °C at a rate of 4 °C/min; helium as the carrier gas at a constant flow rate of 1.0 mL min⁻¹; and an injection volume of 1 µL in split mode (split ratio 1:10).

The mass spectrometer was operated in electron ionization (EI) mode at 70 eV, with the interface, ion source, and quadrupole temperatures maintained at 280 °C, 230 °C, and 200 °C, respectively, and a mass scan range of m/z 35–650 (SAHINGIL, 2019). Retention indices (RI) were calculated using a homologous series of n-alkanes (C7–C30, Sigma-Aldrich, USA) analyzed under identical chromatographic conditions. Compound identification was based on comparison of mass spectra with those in the NIST 20 mass spectral library and on agreement between calculated retention index (RI) values and literature data; authentic reference standards were not employed. The relative abundance of each constituent was estimated by normalization of GC peak areas without application of correction factors.

Antimicrobial activity assay

The antibacterial activity of *M. cajuputi* essential oil was evaluated using the disc diffusion method, following the Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI) guidelines with minor modifications (CLINICAL AND LABORATORY STANDARD INSTITUTE, 2020). The essential oil was prepared at concentrations of 50, 40, 30, 20, and 10 mg/mL. Aliquots of 50 µL from each concentration were aseptically impregnated onto sterile paper discs (6 mm in diameter), air-dried, and used for antibacterial testing.

A bacterial suspension (approximately 1×10^6 CFU/mL) was prepared, and 100 µL was evenly spread onto tryptic soy agar (TSA) plates supplemented with 2% NaCl using a sterile triangular spreader, followed by drying for 3–5 min at room temperature. The impregnated discs were then placed on the inoculated agar surface, and the plates were incubated at 28 °C for 24 h. Discs impregnated with gentamicin (1 mg/mL) were used as positive controls against *E. coli*.

Antibacterial activity was expressed as the diameter of the inhibition zone (IZD, mm) measured after 24 h of incubation at 28 °C.

The minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) and minimum bactericidal concentration (MBC) of *M. cajuputi* essential oil were determined using a broth dilution method adapted from the CLSI guidelines, with modifications to accommodate the low aqueous solubility and relatively weak antibacterial potency of essential oils (CLINICAL AND LABORATORY STANDARD INSTITUTE, 2020). Briefly, a series of essential oil solutions was prepared in sterile broth containing an appropriate emulsifier to obtain final concentrations ranging from 25 to 150 mg/mL. Each test tube contained the essential oil solution and was inoculated with a bacterial suspension adjusted to approximately 1×10^6 CFU/mL. Tubes containing inoculated broth without essential oil served as growth controls, while broth-only tubes were used as sterility controls. All tubes were incubated at 28 °C for 24 h. The MIC was defined as the lowest concentration of essential oil that showed no visible bacterial growth. To determine the MBC, aliquots from tubes exhibiting no visible growth were subcultured onto fresh TSA plates and incubated at 28 °C for an additional 24 h. The MBC was defined as the lowest concentration at which no bacterial colonies were observed, corresponding to a $\geq 99.9\%$ reduction in the initial bacterial population.

α -Glucosidase inhibitory activity

The α -glucosidase inhibitory activity of *M. cajuputi* essential oil was assessed following the method reported by Nguyen et al. (2017), with minor modifications. Briefly, 50 μ L of the essential-oil solution prepared in 0.1 M phosphate buffer (pH 6.8) at various concentrations (1500, 750.0, 375.0, 187.5, 93.75, and 46.875 μ g/mL) was mixed with 30 μ L of α -glucosidase solution (2 U/mL). The reaction mixture was pre-incubated at 37 °C for 10 min. Subsequently, 50 μ L of 2.5 mM *p*NPG prepared in the same phosphate buffer was added to initiate the

enzymatic reaction, followed by incubation at 37 °C for an additional 30 min. The absorbance of the released *p*-nitrophenol was measured at 405 nm using a microplate reader (BIO-RAD iMark). A control reaction containing solvent instead of the essential oil was prepared in parallel.

The percentage inhibition of α -glucosidase activity was calculated using Equation (1):

$$\text{Inhibition (\%)} = \frac{A_0 - A_1}{A_0} \times 100\% \quad (1)$$

where A_0 represents the absorbance of the control reaction containing solvent only, and A_1 denotes the absorbance measured for the test sample under identical experimental conditions (NGUYEN et al., 2017).

Anti-inflammatory activity

The anti-inflammatory potential of the essential oil was assessed using the inhibition of protein denaturation assay, adapted from the method reported by Shah et al. (2017) (SHAH et al., 2017). Briefly, 1 mL of the test solution prepared at different concentrations (800, 400, 200, 100, 50, and 25 μ g/mL) was mixed with 1 mL of 5% bovine serum albumin (BSA). The mixture was incubated at 27 °C for 15 min and subsequently subjected to heat-induced denaturation at 60 °C for 10 min. After cooling to room temperature, the absorbance was measured at 660 nm. Diclofenac was used as the reference anti-inflammatory agent.

The percentage inhibition of protein denaturation (I, %) was calculated using Equation (2):

$$I (\%) = \left(1 - \frac{V_t}{V_c}\right) \times 100\% \quad (2)$$

where V_t represents the absorbance of the reaction mixture containing the essential oil or the reference drug, and V_c denotes the absorbance of the control mixture containing phosphate buffer only.

A calibration curve was constructed by plotting the percentage inhibition of BSA denaturation against the concentration of the test samples. The IC_{50} value, defined as the

concentration required to inhibit 50% of protein denaturation, was calculated from the linear regression equation ($y = ax + b$).

Molecular docking and ADMET (absorption, distribution, metabolism, excretion, toxicity) predictions of studied compounds

The three-dimensional crystal structures of *E. coli* DNA GyrB (PDB ID: 6F86), *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* α -glucosidase (PDB ID: 3AJ7), and iNOS (PDB ID: 3E7G) were retrieved from the RCSB Protein Data Bank. Protein preparation was carried out using UCSF Chimera version 1.19, including the removal of non-standard residues. Polar hydrogen atoms were added, and Gasteiger charges were assigned using the Dock Prep module.

The ligand structures of the thirteen selected volatile constituents, and the reference compounds gentamicin, acarbose, and diclofenac were generated based on their respective PubChem compound identifiers using the Build Structure tool in UCSF Chimera. Ligand preparation involved the addition of hydrogen atoms, assignment of Gasteiger charges via Dock Prep, and subsequent energy minimization using the Minimize Structure tool. All prepared proteins and ligands were saved in PDB format for docking calculations.

Molecular docking simulations were performed using AutoDock Vina version 1.2.5 integrated within UCSF Chimera. Potential binding pockets of the target proteins were identified using the DoGSiteScorer server, and the highest-ranked binding sites were selected based on their scoring functions and predicted probabilities (KHAN & UDDIN, 2022). Grid boxes were centered on the selected binding pockets to fully encompass the key interacting residues. Docking calculations were carried out using the Broyden–Fletcher–Goldfarb–Shanno (BFGS) optimization algorithm, generating up to ten binding conformations per ligand. Default AutoDock Vina parameters were applied throughout the docking process. Docked poses were

ranked according to binding affinity, and the conformation with the lowest binding energy was selected for further interaction analysis.

All docking simulations were conducted on a Windows 10 Pro workstation equipped with an Intel Core i5 processor (2.53 GHz). Drug-likeness of the investigated compounds was evaluated based on Lipinski's rule of five (LIPINSKI, 2000). Pharmacokinetic and physicochemical properties were predicted using the SwissADME web server (BAKCHI et al., 2022), while acute oral toxicity was predicted using the ProTox-3 web server (BANERJEE et al., 2024).

Statistical analysis

Antibacterial activity in the disc diffusion assay was expressed as mean \pm standard deviation (SD) from three independent measurements. For the broth dilution assay, MIC and MBC values were recorded as the lowest concentrations showing inhibition of visible growth and bactericidal effect, respectively, according to the assay criteria. For the α -glucosidase inhibitory and anti-inflammatory assays, concentration-dependent inhibitory effects were calculated relative to the corresponding controls, and IC₅₀ values were estimated from the concentration–response data. No formal inferential statistical comparison among treatment groups was applied in these preliminary bioassays.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

p-Cymene

Interactions:
 von der Waals
 Pi-Pi Stacked
 Alkyl
 Pi-Alkyl

Eucalyptol

Interactions:
 von der Waals
 Conventional Hydrogen Bond
 Alkyl
 Pi-Alkyl

β -Phellandrene

Interactions:
 von der Waals
 Alkyl
 Pi-Alkyl

cis-Pinane

Interactions:
 von der Waals
 Alkyl
 Pi-Alkyl

3-Carene

Interactions:
 von der Waals
 Alkyl
 Pi-Alkyl

α -Terpineol

Interactions:
 von der Waals
 Conventional Hydrogen Bond
 Alkyl
 Pi-Alkyl

2-Carene

Interactions:
 von der Waals
 Alkyl
 Pi-Alkyl

Pinocarveol

Interactions:
 von der Waals
 Alkyl
 Pi-Alkyl

δ -Selinene

Interactions:
 von der Waals
 Pi-Pi Stacked
 Alkyl
 Pi-Alkyl

β -Patchoulene

Interactions:
 von der Waals
 Alkyl
 Pi-Alkyl

Figure 4 - 2D and 3D visualization of target compounds and acarbose on the 3AJ7 protein.

Figure 5 - 2D and 3D visualization of target compounds and diclofenac on the iNOS protein.

Table 4. Binding and interactions of the studied compounds and reference compound on protein 6F86.

Compounds	Docking score (kcal/mol)	Hydrogen bonds	Hydrophobic interactions	Other interactions
α -Pinene	-4.562	- ^a	Ile78	-
Sabinene	-4.798	-	Ile78	-
<i>p</i> -Cymene	-5.014	-	Ile78	-
Eucalyptol	-4.603	-	Ile78	-
β -Phellandrene	-5.150	-	Ile78	-
<i>cis</i> -Pinane	-4.474	-	Ile78, Pro79	-
3-Carene	-4.995	-	Ile78	-
α -Terpineol	-5.086	Glu50	Ile78, Pro79, Arg76	-
2-Carene	-4.959	-	Ile78	-
Pinocarveol	-5.216	-	Ile78	-
δ -Selinene	-6.258	-	Ile78, Ile94	-
β -Patchoulene	-6.396	-	Ile78, Ile95	-
<i>trans</i> -Caryophyllene	-5.475	-	Ile78, Ala53, Pro79, Ile94	-
Gentamicin	-6.477	Gly77, Asn46	Val120	Arg136, Glu50, Asp49, Asp73

^a Not forming hydrogen bonds and other interactions

Table 5 - Binding and interactions of studied compounds and reference compounds on the 3AJ7 protein.

Compounds	Docking score (kcal/mol)	Hydrogen bonds	Hydrophobic interactions	Other interactions
α -Pinene	-5.820	- ^a	Phe314, Ala418, Ile419, His423	-
Sabinene	-6.188	-	Phe314, His423, Ile419, Ala418	-
<i>p</i> -Cymene	-6.474	-	Phe314, Ile419	-
Eucalyptol	-5.649	Arg442	Tyr158, Phe178, Phe303	-
β -Phellandrene	-6.512	-	Ala418, Phe314	-
<i>cis</i> -Pinane	-5.501	-	Phe303, Tyr158, Val216, Phe178	-
3-Carene	-6.339	-	His423, Ala418, Ile419, Phe314	-
α -Terpineol	-6.654	His423	Ile419, Phe314, Lys156	-
2-Carene	-6.318	-	His423, Ala418, Ile419, Phe314	-
Pinocarveol	-6.064	-	His423, Ala418, Ile419, Phe315	-
δ -Selinene	-7.496	-	Tyr158, Phe314, Lys156, Arg315	-

β -Patchoulene	-7.036	-	Arg315, Lys156, Tyr158, His280	-
<i>trans</i> - Caryophyllene	-6.768	-	Phe178, Arg315, Tyr158	-
			Ser157, Tyr158, Asp215, Glu277, Asp352, Asp307	
Acarbose	-8.920	Tyr158, Asp215, Glu277, Asp352, Asp307, Phe314, Arg315	-	Leu313, Lys156

^a Not forming hydrogen bonds, hydrophobic and other interactions.

Table 6 - Binding and interactions of studied compounds and reference compounds on the iNOS protein.

Compound	Dock score (kcal/mol)	Hydrogen bonds	Hydrophobic interactions	Other interactions
α -Pinene	-5.120	- ^a	Trp194, Phe269, Cys200	-
Sabinene	-5.855	-	Phe488, Tyr489, Arg199, Pro198, Ala197, Leu125, Met355, Phe369	-
<i>p</i> -Cymene	-7.721	-	Trp194, Leu209, Ala197, Cys200	-
Eucalyptol	-5.143	Gly371	Trp194, Pro350, Phe369, Val352, Cys200	-
β -Phellandrene	-7.332	-	Trp194, Tyr489, Phe369, Ile244, Cys200, Leu209	-
<i>cis</i> -Pinane	-4.846	-	Cys200, Ala197, Met355, Tyr491, Trp463, Arg199, Pro198, Phe488	-

3-Carene	-5.845	-		Phe369, Cys200, Tyr489, Trp194	-
α -Terpineol	-7.105	Gly371		Phe369, Cys200, Trp194, Leu209, Tyr489	-
2-Carene	-5.940	-		Phe369, Cys200, Trp194, Tyr489	-
Pinocarveol	-5.377	Asp382		Val352	-
δ -Selinene	-7.989	-		Cys200, Ala197, Val352, Arg199, Met355, Trp463, Leu125, Tyr491	-
β -Patchoulene	-6.305	-		Trp463, Pro467, Arg381, Met374 Leu125, Tyr491, Pro198, Ala197,	-
<i>trans</i> -Caryophyllene	-6.646	-		Arg199, Phe488, Met355, Tyr489, Phe369, Val352	-
Diclofenac	-8.522	Trp372, Ser242		Pro350, Asn370, Trp194, Phe369	-

^a Not forming hydrogen bonds, hydrophobic and other interactions.

Table 7 - Physicochemical properties, lipophilicity, and water solubility of compounds studied by using SwissADME.

Compound	MW (g/mol)	LogP	nHBD	nHBA	TPSA (Å ²)	MR	Lipinski violation	LogS (ESOL)	nRotB
α -Pinene	136.23	3.44	0	0	0	45.22	1	-3.51	0
Sabinene	136.23	3.25	0	0	0	45.22	1	-2.57	1
<i>p</i> -Cymene	134.22	3.50	0	0	0	45.99	1	-3.63	1
Eucalyptol	154.25	2.67	0	1	9.23	47.12	0	-2.52	0
β -Phellandrene	136.23	3.07	0	0	0	47.12	0	-2.79	1
<i>cis</i> -Pinane	138.25	3.37	0	0	0	45.70	1	-3.15	0

3-Carene	136.23	3.42	0	0	0	45.22	1	-3.44	0
α -Terpineol	154.25	2.58	1	1	20.23	48.80	0	-2.87	1
2-Carene	136.23	3.12	0	0	0	45.22	1	-2.48	0
Pinocarveol	152.23	2.07	1	1	20.23	46.38	0	-1.91	0
δ -Selinene	204.35	4.34	0	0	0	68.78	1	-3.76	1
β -Patchoulene	204.35	4.40	0	0	0	66.88	1	-3.81	0
<i>trans</i> - Caryophyllene	204.35	4.24	0	0	0	68.78	1	-3.87	0
Gentamicin	477.60	-2.15	8	12	199.73	118.31	2	0.24	7
Acarbose	645.60	-6.24	14	19	329.01	137.92	3	2.57	13
Diclofenac	296.15	3.66	2	2	49.33	77.55	0	-4.65	4

MW: molecular weight; LogP: log of octanol/water partition coefficient; nHBD: number of hydrogen bond donors; nHBA: number of hydrogen bond acceptors; TPSA: topological polar surface area; MR: molar refractivity; nRotB: number of rotatable bonds.

Table 8 - Pharmacokinetics predictions of studied compounds computed by SwissADME.

Compound	LogK _p (cm/s)	GI Abs	BBB per	Inhibitor interaction					
				P-gp substrate	CYP1A2 inhibitor	CYP2C19 inhibitor	CYP2C9 inhibitor	CYP2D6 inhibitor	CYP3A4 inhibitor
α -Pinene	-3.95	Low	Yes	No	No	No	Yes	No	No
Sabinene	-4.94	Low	Yes	No	No	No	No	No	No
<i>p</i> -Cymene	-4.21	Low	Yes	No	No	No	No	Yes	No
Eucalyptol	-5.30	High	Yes	No	No	No	No	No	No
β -Phellandrene	-4.69	Low	Yes	No	No	No	No	No	No

<i>cis</i> -Pinane	-4.37	Low	Yes	No	No	No	Yes	No	No
3-Carene	-4.02	Low	Yes	No	No	No	Yes	No	No
α -Terpineol	-4.83	High	Yes	No	No	No	No	No	No
2-Carene	-5.11	Low	Yes	No	No	No	No	No	No
Pinocarveol	-5.96	High	Yes	No	No	No	No	No	No
δ -Selinene	-4.49	Low	No	No	No	No	Yes	No	No
β -Patchoulene	-4.50	Low	No	No	No	Yes	Yes	No	No
<i>trans</i> -Caryophyllene	-4.44	Low	No	No	No	Yes	Yes	No	No
Gentamicin	-12.12	Low	No	Yes	No	No	No	No	No
Acarbose	-16.50	Low	No	Yes	No	No	No	No	No
Diclofenac	-4.98	High	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No

GI Abs: gastrointestinal absorption; BBB per: blood-brain barrier permeability; P-gp: P-glycoprotein; CYP: cytochrome P.

Table 9 - Toxicity prediction results by ProTox 3.0.

Compound	LD ₅₀ (mg/kg) ^a	Classification
α -Pinene	3700	V
Sabinene	5000	V
<i>p</i> -Cymene	3	I
Eucalyptol	2480	V
β -Phellandrene	5000	V
<i>cis</i> -Pinane	15380	VI
3-Carene	4800	V
α -Terpineol	2830	V

2-Carene	4800	V
Pinocarveol	5000	V
δ -Selinene	7000	VI
β -Patchoulene	5000	V
<i>trans</i> -Caryophyllene	5300	V
Gentamicin	5000	V
Acarbose	2000	IV
<hr/>		
Diclofenac	53	III
<hr/>		

^a LD₅₀: lethal dose, 50%